

The Effects of X-Radiation in a Quasi-Low-Dropout Voltage Regulator

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Abstract—The aim of this paper was to test the possibility of implementation of the commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) quasi-low-dropout voltage regulator in a harsh bremsstrahlung environment (in the case of a lifelong exposure to moderate total ionising doses). Results of examination of the LT1086CT5 voltage regulator, performed in the field of X-rays, are presented in this paper. Biased and loaded circuits demonstrated acceptable characteristics in the bremsstrahlung environment for total doses up to 433 Gy, but some samples of unbiased circuits demonstrated unacceptable decline of the output voltage even after absorption of ionising dose of 260 Gy. One-week room temperature annealing led to a further degradation of all of the irradiated voltage regulators, both unbiased and biased, during irradiation. All the examined samples remained functional, but pointed to numerous limitations for implementation of these COTS voltage regulators in an ionising radiation environment.

Index Terms—Voltage regulator; X-rays; bipolar transistor; radiation effects.

I. INTRODUCTION

IMPLEMENTATION of the commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) integrated circuits, instead of the specially designed “rad-hard” components, is now a long-lasting trend [1]. The main reason is related to the much lower price of the COTS components, as well as the considerably wider portfolio of the available integrated circuit made by the use of modern technological processes [1]. Among the serious candidates for implementation of COTS solutions are power integrated circuits. Low-dropout voltage regulators belong to this class of electronic devices [2]-[5], being particularly important to the point-of-load, low-current power supply of small load (being in the order of several hundred milliamps), as well as the battery powered electronic circuits [6].

In previous years, many efforts were made to examine the possibility of implementation of the COTS low-dropout voltage regulators with various power transistors and control circuit topologies [7]-[9]. Nevertheless, among three different topologies of low-dropout voltage regulators, also one quasi-low-dropout circuit, LT1086CT5, was examined, utilising the NPN power transistor as a pass element [10]. This circuit was a potential candidate for implementation in a moderate radiation environment.

In this paper, examination of characteristics of the LT1086CT5 voltage regulator was presented. Radiation effects caused by total absorbed doses of the braking ionising

radiation (bremsstrahlung), up to 433 Gy, were described, followed by a short term 168-hour room temperature annealing.

II. THEORY

A. Configuration of Low-Dropout Voltage Regulators

One of the basic characteristics for evaluation of voltage regulators is a dropout voltage that is a minimum voltage across a serial (pass) transistor that enables this integrated circuit to maintain a stable voltage on its output terminal [11]. The main difference between configuration of a low-dropout (a) and a quasi-low-dropout (b) voltage regulator is presented in Fig. 1. In a low-dropout voltage regulator, a PNP power transistor may be independent pass element (Qp), so a dropout voltage is equal only to the collector – emitter voltage of a serial transistor [11]. In a quasi-low-dropout voltage regulator, an NPN transistor (Qp1) should be driven by a collector current of accompanying PNP transistor [11] (Qp2). Thus, dropout voltage is now the sum of a PNP driver transistor emitter-base voltage and a serial NPN transistor collector – emitter voltage [11].

Fig. 1. Topologies of voltage regulators: a) low-dropout; b) quasi-low-dropout.

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A negative consequence of implementing a combination of an ordinary PNP and an NPN power transistor as a pass element is primarily related to the increase of a dropout voltage (approximately 1.2-1.5 V for a nominal load, in comparison with approximately 0.6-0.8 V in a case when a PNP power transistor was utilised [11]). On the other hand, the advantage of using an NPN power transistor is related to its operation with much lower base current and, consequently, much lower quiescent current of the entire voltage regulator.

B. Radiation and Post-Irradiation Effects in Bipolar Transistors and Integrated Circuits

The primary effect that ionising radiation has on a bipolar junction transistor is related to the increase of its base current, consequently leading to reduction of the forward emitter current gain [1]. This excess base current is primarily a result of the charge becoming trapped in the isolation oxide and at the semiconductor-oxide interface above the base area [1]. In general form, the relation for the excess base current (ΔI_B) in an irradiated bipolar transistor may be presented as [12]:

$$\Delta I_B = I_B - I_{B0} = \frac{1}{2} q n_i P_E s(N_{ot}, N_{it}, V_{BE}) \gamma(N_{ot}, V_{BE}) e^{\frac{V_{BE}}{V_T}} \quad (1)$$

where: I_B – base current after irradiation, I_{B0} – base current before irradiation, q – elementary electron charge ($1.6 \cdot 10^{-19}$ C), n_i – intrinsic carrier concentration in silicon, P_E – length of the emitter perimeter, N_{ot} – concentration of the oxide traps, N_{it} – concentration of the interface traps, V_{BE} – voltage on the junction base – emitter, $s(N_{ot}, N_{it}, V_{BE})$ – surface recombination velocity, a function of the specified electrical values, $\gamma(N_{ot}, V_{BE})$ – an integral describing the depletion region spreading over the intrinsic base [13], and V_T – thermal voltage (26 mV at 20°C).

The other mechanism that primarily affects a PNP bipolar transistor forward emitter current gain is related to similar effects above the emitter area, causing the spread of the base-emitter depletion region deep into the P-type emitter area [14]. Thus, oxide-trapped charge and interface traps above the base and emitter areas are the main cause of the characteristic degradation of a bipolar transistor operating in an ionising radiation environment [14]. Above the P-type area, the effects of the interface and oxide traps are complementary, both leading to degradation of a semiconductor device [14]. Usually, the excess base current of the PNP transistor is considered to be primarily affected by the influence of interface traps [14], while NPN transistors are considered to be mostly affected by the oxide-trapped charge [12]. The following empirical relations are a good illustration of the mentioned phenomena [15]:

$$\Delta I_B \sim N_{it} e^{N_{ot}^2}, \text{ for an NPN transistor} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta I_B \sim N_{it} \frac{1}{N_{ot}^2}, \text{ for an PNP transistor} \quad (3)$$

Bias conditions also have great impact on the radiation response of a bipolar transistor or integrated circuit based on such an element. While the positive electrical field in the oxide may suppress build-up of the oxide-trapped charge, the negative bias voltage may suppress or even prevent build-up of interface traps [16]. Usually, the most damaging effect may

be observed in bipolar transistors and integrated circuits exposed to the influence of ionising radiation without any bias voltage [1]. In these cases, very high excess base currents may be recorded, and both interface traps and the oxide-trapped charge may have great influence on the degradation of a bipolar transistor current gain. On the other hand, operation of the bipolar transistor with high dissipation may significantly reduce its radiation damage and even prevent the integrated circuit failure [3, 9], both due to the high increase of a chip temperature (followed by an annealing of the trapped charge) or operation with high-current-density at the base-emitter area [3].

After the end of ionising radiation exposure, bipolar transistors may demonstrate recovery, or further degradation of their electrical characteristics [1]. Owing to a type of its post-irradiation response, often a trustworthy conclusion may be drawn regarding the mechanism of the bipolar transistor radiation response [1]. The post-irradiation response of an irradiated bipolar transistor is highly temperature dependant. Thus, high temperature annealing may lead to recovery of both oxide-trapped charge (this process becomes more expressed as temperature increases up to 100°C [16, 17]) and interface traps (dominates when temperatures are in the range 150-250°C [17]). Nevertheless, even at a room temperature of nearly 20°C, trapped charge may be recovered, primarily due to the tunnelling mechanism [16]. Thus, room temperature recovery of bipolar transistors is also described by the word “annealing”. Recovery of the oxide-trapped charge may be accompanied by further interface trap build-up [18]. In such a case, forward emitter current gain of a bipolar transistor may be additionally reduced. On the other hand, if the oxide-trapped charge had significant influence on the excess base current then the annealing of this charge may lead to an expressed recovery of the forward emitter current gain of an irradiated bipolar transistor.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Radiation Source and Dosimetry

The samples of LT1086CT5 voltage regulator, an integrated circuit made by *Linear Technology*[®], were tested at the Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, in the Metrology-Dosimetric laboratory. As a source of X-rays, the *Philips*[®] MG320 dosimetric generator was used. The continuous spectrum of braking radiation was obtained using a voltage of 300 kV and a current of 10 mA, with implementation of a tungsten target. Thus, photon spectrum, with energies up to 300 keV, was obtained [9]. Primary filtration of a photon spectrum was obtained with 4-mm-thick embedded aluminium foil [9]. In order to obtain additional filtration, another 0.47-mm-thick aluminium foil was added [9]. As a result, all the photons with energies lower than 37 keV were removed from the spectrum [19]. Consequently, a bremsstrahlung field was obtained, having a mean energy of 170 keV [9].

Exposure measurement was performed with a cavity ionising chamber *Dosimetric*[®] PTW M23361 [7]. The D14 reader was used during the measurement [7]. With these instruments, exposure in Roentgen (R) was procured, and,

recalculated further for the total absorbed dose in silicon-dioxide ($Gy(SiO_2)$) [9] using X-ray mass attenuation coefficients for air and silicon-dioxide [20]. Using the dosimetric chamber, the exposure rate was measured to be $F = 340 \text{ R/min} = 20,400 \text{ R/h}$. In standard temperature and pressure (STP) dry air, the following relation is valid [17]: $1 \text{ R} = 0.84 \text{ rad(air)} = 0.84 \text{ cGy(air)}$.

Since the integrated circuit is comprised of the multiple, micrometer-thick layers, only an approximate calculation was made. The kinetic energy of the primary charged particles released by photons, enhanced by the contribution of charged particles travelling through the silicon-dioxide [20], had the crucial influence to the total dose response of bipolar transistors in an integrated circuit. For the nearest available value of the mean photon energy in the table of mass-energy absorption coefficients, that is 150 keV, coefficients were extracted for the air and the silicon-dioxide (borosilicate glass) [20]: $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}(SiO_2) = 2.727 \cdot 10^{-2} \frac{cm^2}{g}$, $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}(air) = 2.496 \cdot 10^{-2} \frac{cm^2}{g}$. According to the available data, the dose rate in silicon-dioxide (reduced to cGy) was calculated as [17, 20]:

$$\frac{dD}{dt}(SiO_2) = F \cdot 0.84 \cdot \frac{\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}(SiO_2)}{\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}(air)} \quad (4)$$

Finally, total dose rate (in $Gy(SiO_2)$) was:

$$\frac{dD}{dt}(SiO_2) = 187.2 \frac{Gy}{h} \quad (5)$$

Therefore, in the 170-keV effective X-rays field ($V_{TUBE} = 300 \text{ kV}$, $I_{TUBE} = 10 \text{ mA}$), dose rate for silicon-dioxide was $187.2 \text{ Gy}(SiO_2)/h$. Measurements were performed after deposition of the following total ionising doses (in $Gy(SiO_2)$): 0; 43.3; 86.7; 130; 173.3; 260; 346.7; 433. One additional measurement was performed after 168-hour room temperature annealing (without implementation of any bias and load) of the irradiated samples.

B. Electrical Characteristics

Samples of LT1086CT5 voltage regulators were tested in a field of X-rays with two various operating conditions: without bias and load ($V_{IN} = 0 \text{ V}$, $I_{OUT} = 0 \text{ A}$), as well as with input bias voltage and load current ($V_{IN} = 7 \text{ V}$, $I_{OUT} = 100 \text{ mA}$) during operation in the ionising radiation environment. In order to enable the voltage regulator operation in the X-rays field, exposed samples were supplied with 10 m long cables [7]. In order to enable remote measurement of the output voltage at the terminals of voltage regulators, the sensing cables of the same length were laid alongside the power supply cables [7]. The power source of DC voltage enabled simultaneous supply up to four electrically isolated integrated circuits [7]. Irradiation of components and measurement were performed at a room temperature of 20°C [7].

Electrical characteristics used for evaluation of the voltage

regulator degradation in the X-rays environment were the maximum output current and the minimum dropout voltage. The maximum output current was procured in the measurement point where the voltage regulator input voltage was set to 8 V DC, while the output voltage declined down to 4.7 V (this is a value close to the point when voltage regulator commence the shutdown procedure) [8]. The minimum dropout voltage was obtained for a constant load current of 400 mA and a constant output voltage of 4.9 V [8].

IV. RESULTS

In Fig. 2 were presented variations of the maximum output current in the field of 170-keV X-rays, obtained for unbiased as well as biased and loaded voltage regulators. As initially expected, unbiased circuits demonstrated greater degradation of the maximum output current than the biased ones. So, while biased circuits demonstrated degradation of the maximum output current up to 7% of the initial value, exposure to X-rays reduced the same parameter in unbiased voltage regulators up to 20%. However, for a total dose of 433 Gy, such reduction may be acceptable if the integrated circuit kept its functionality as a power source with a stable five-volt output.

Fig. 3. shows the results on variations of the minimum dropout voltage obtained on the same samples of the LT1086CT5 voltage regulator in a bremsstrahlung environment. This test gave much more questioning results regarding this voltage regulator radiation hardness.

Fig. 2. Change in the maximum output current of LT1086CT5 voltage regulators in the X-rays field.

At first, a comment has to be made regarding the high initial values of the minimum dropout voltage, being approximately 3 V. This relatively high value is a consequence of the low filter capacitance (nominally $330 \mu\text{F}$) [8] at the output of the Gretz diode bridge, being a converter of the (transformed) mains AC voltage to a DC voltage at the input terminal of a voltage regulator. Therefore, input voltage on a voltage regulator had a very high AC component affecting the voltage regulator operation, particularly with

high load currents. Nonetheless, such a measurement configuration did not negatively affect procured results on the integrated circuit radiation tolerance.

Fig. 3. Change in the minimum dropout voltage of LT1086CT5 voltage regulators in the X-rays field.

The data obtained for unbiased voltage regulators presented in Fig. 3 point to the significant increase of the minimum dropout voltage after deposition of the total dose of 260 Gy. Dropout voltage reached unacceptably high values after the final dose of 433 Gy was achieved. The more careful examination of individual irradiated samples points to the inability of one sample (out of a total of five) to obtain an output voltage of 4.9 V (following absorption of the total dose of 260 Gy). Then, after deposition of 433 Gy, another unbiased sample decreased its output voltage below the mentioned threshold of 4.9 V, bringing the number of unacceptable circuits up to two. Therefore, even to obtain such a reduced voltage, the much higher input voltage had to be applied. Therefore, it led to an increase of the mean value of the minimum dropout voltage of unbiased samples up to 8 V (Fig. 3). It is important to emphasise that none of the biased and loaded samples expressed a similar phenomenon, with all five samples being completely functional, simultaneously having a dropout voltage across a serial transistor being marginally higher from its pre-irradiation value.

V. DISCUSSION

As may be seen from Figs. 2 and 3, in both cases one-week, room temperature isothermal annealing led to a further degradation of irradiated voltage regulators, regardless of their bias conditions during bremsstrahlung exposure. Such a post-irradiation response suggests interface traps as the primary influence on degradation of the critical bipolar transistors. As previously mentioned, physical mechanism that affected the voltage regulator response is related with a partial recovery of the oxide-trapped charge, accompanied by a simultaneous build-up of interface traps. At a first glance, this is a little surprising, since it would be expected that the oxide-trapped

charge would have a dominant influence on the serial power NPN transistor. Taking into account the perceived effects, a rise of the power NPN transistor excess base current may be expected, consequently leading to a decline of its forward emitter current gain. Additionally, radiation response of a voltage regulator is not only dictated by a serial power transistor and, furthermore, some small-signal transistors may have a decisive effect on its operation characteristics. It should be brought to mind that, in a quasi-low-dropout voltage regulator, a driver PNP transistor is also a part of the pass element.

Since the photons in bremsstrahlung spectrum contain energies from 37 keV up to 300 keV, there certainly exists possibility for violation of the charged-particle equilibrium (CPE) in the examined integrated circuit. Nonetheless, it was assumed that, looking chip-wide, CPE wouldn't be violated in the active areas of bipolar transistors, situated at the interface Si – SiO₂. Potentially critical areas for the dose enhancement are connections between metallizations and the chip of an integrated circuit [17]. Most of these connections are situated at the bottom of integrated circuit, thus being far away from the active area, right beneath the insulation oxide [17]. Nonetheless, metallizations from the top side of the case, connecting the output leads of voltage regulator with semiconductor, may cause dose enhancement in silicon, if the connection material has a much higher atomic number [16] (in this case, relative to silicon (Si): $Z = 14$). Usually, metals used for such connections are copper (Cu; $Z = 29$) or gold (Au; $Z = 79$). Since the copper doesn't have much higher atomic number than silicon, significant dose enhancement should not be expected. Nonetheless, completely different situation may appear if gold is used. In that case, charged-particle equilibrium may be locally violated. The author did not have insight into the exact material composition of the implemented TO-220 case, used for packaging of the LT1086CT5 voltage regulator. Thus, it was assumed that, chip-wide, for the calculation of the total ionising dose in the insulation layer of SiO₂, CPE was achieved. Nonetheless, it is not impossible that locally, at the connections of some of three output leads with chip, dose enhancement exists. However, it was assumed that the mentioned effect could be distinctively expressed only in some small-signal transistors, and that the serial NPN power transistor is too large to be notably affected by the violation of the CPE.

In general, quasi-low-dropout voltage regulator demonstrated significant sensitivity to the influence of X-rays. A total dose of 260 Gy(SiO₂), being a threshold value when unacceptable degradation was observed in unbiased samples, is lower than expected before the examination. Nonetheless, this was certainly not an example of the extremely low radiation hardness of an analogue integrated circuit. As already presented in the literature [17], threshold of radiation tolerance may vary for several orders of magnitude, depending on the batch of integrated circuit, manufacturer's technological process, bias conditions during the irradiation, as well as the characteristics of the ionising radiation environment (types of spectra, mean photon energy, dose rate,

etc.). The author of this article detected failure of some samples of LM2990T-5 LDO voltage regulators even at the bremsstrahlung total dose as low as 37 Gy(SiO₂) [9], regardless the fact that samples from the same lot in γ -radiation field remained completely functional even after absorption of the total dose of 500 Gy (SiO₂) [9].

In manuals and handbooks may be found approximate data on radiation tolerance of various types of semiconductor devices and integrated circuits. For instance, in the document [21], radiation tolerance of CMOS operational amplifiers (Op Amp) was estimated to be up to 100 Gy [21], while the same parameter for bipolar Op Amps was estimated to be 1 – 2.5 kGy [21]. In the same document, low-dropout voltage regulators were estimated to be radiation tolerant for total ionising doses up to 300 – 500 Gy [21]. Nonetheless, in the same document, there were specified several *National Semiconductor*[®] regulators, having the stated radiation hardness threshold exceeding 1 kGy [21]. Tolerance to very high total doses of ionising radiation is usually characteristic of the specially designed, rad-hard semiconductor devices and integrated circuits.

The main goal of the research presented in this paper was to examine the possibility of implementation of cheap COTS integrated circuits instead of the very expensive, specially designed rad-hard components. The additional motive for the presented research was the existence of a practically the same component, of the same manufacturer, LT1086MH/883, yet declared for implementation in the harsh radiation environments. According to the performed tests, a conclusion can be made that unbiased LT1086CT5 circuits are not suitable for bremsstrahlung environments where deposition of the total dose greater than 200 Gy(SiO₂) may be expected. Nevertheless, none of the examined circuit demonstrated a functional failure for total ionising doses up to 433 Gy(SiO₂).

Thus, a complex research has to be made, in various radiation fields, prior to qualification of some semiconductor component for exploitation in a radiation environment. In general, implemented technological processes for the synthesis of semiconductor chips (and particular quality of the insulation oxides) dominantly affect the radiation response of an analogue integrated circuit.

VI. CONCLUSION

Quasi-low-dropout voltage regulators, LT1086CT5, were tested for possibility of implementation in the ionising radiation environment. Regarding these quasi-LDO regulators, for the first time was presented data on the maximum output current and the minimum dropout voltage (recorded with a high load current). Also, results on the one-week, room-temperature annealing are novel data for the irradiated *Linear Technology*[®] LT1086CT5 COTS voltage regulators.

In the effective 170-keV X-rays field, for a medium dose rate (187.2 Gy(SiO₂)/h), samples of this COTS circuit were tested for two various modes of operation during the exposure: unbiased, as well as with bias and load ($V_{IN} = 7$ V,

$I_{OUT} = 100$ mA). For the total ionising dose of 433 Gy(SiO₂), biased samples demonstrated higher radiation tolerance than the unbiased. Nevertheless, the maximum output current recorded in unbiased samples of LT1086CT5 voltage regulators did not fall below 80 % of their pre-irradiation values. Less acceptable were the values of the minimum dropout voltage (for $I_{OUT} = 400$ mA), particularly due to a decline of the output voltage below the minimum acceptable value of 4.9 V, recorded on some of the tested samples. Also, cause for concern was further degradation of electrical parameters used in all the tested circuits (regardless of their bias conditions during irradiation), noticed during the following room temperature, one-week isothermal annealing sequence. Experimental results support the conclusion that unbiased LT1086CT5 voltage regulators are not suitable for bremsstrahlung environments where lifelong absorption of the total dose greater than 200 Gy(SiO₂) may be expected. Nonetheless, recorded radiation response leaves a possibility that these voltage regulators may be satisfactorily exploited in the radiation environment as continuously biased circuits, operating with load currents being, for an order of magnitude, lower than the voltage regulator nominal output current.

Procured results could not lead to an unambiguous conclusion on the radiation tolerance of these COTS voltage regulators. Presented results were related only to a medium-photon-energy bremsstrahlung field, and for two types of operating conditions. Thus, it was not sufficient to make a final conclusion on the possibility to implement this analogue integrated circuit in all kinds of ionising radiation environments. Therefore, in order to get a complete insight into this circuit's ionising radiation hardness, it would be necessary to perform also its detailed examination in the field of γ -radiation, with more different bias and load conditions, as well as for total ionising doses exceeding 433 Gy(SiO₂). Finally, only separation of radiation effects in small-signal transistors, on the one hand, and the power transistor, on the other, could enable the precise identification of the failure mechanisms of a quasi-low-dropout voltage regulator LT1086CT5, affected by the influence of an ionising radiation environment.

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